

STUDY ON KOREAN PROVERBS BY KOREAN FOLKLORISTS

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Annotation. *This article discusses the origin of Korean folk proverbs and the history of their collection, as well as the theories expressed by Korean linguists about proverbs.*

Key words: *Korean folk proverbs, history of studying Korean folk proverbs, dictionary of Korean proverbs, theories about proverbs.*

Man can understand the world and himself through a language that embodies universal and national socio-historical experiences. A person's interest in the past and culture also forces him to pay close attention to language. The echoes of the past, the joys and sorrows, the intellect and wisdom, the experiences and conclusions of life are today reflected in the examples of folklore, such as proverbs and sayings. As the Russian linguist F.I. Buslayev explains, paremias are specific microworlds that express the moral rules and common sense left by ancestors to guide their descendants [1, p.206]. That is why proverbs and sayings are widely studied today not only in the fields of folklore and linguistics, but also in such fields as cultural studies, ethnolinguistics and ethnography.

Korean folk proverbs, like Uzbek folk proverbs, are complex and one of the best examples of folklore. The Encyclopedia of Korean Culture states that there are two main reasons for the emergence of Korean folk proverbs:

- 1) proverbs formed from the description of a certain historical situation;
- 2) proverbs based on the description of common situations that occur in everyday life.

Most Korean folk proverbs are derived from descriptions of situations that occur in the daily lives of ordinary people. However, they may include well-known names: names of historical figures, names of literary works, names of regions [7]. For example, if we translate the proverb “황정승 네 치마 하나 세 모녀가 돌려 입듯” into Uzbek, it means “*Hvang Jong-singning uyida uch ayol bir libosni bo'lishib kiyadi*”. Hwang Jong-sing, a prominent politician of the Koryo and Chosun eras and later prime minister, was known for his extremely frugal lifestyle, and people even joked that his wife and daughters share a dress in his house. Gradually, this joke became a proverb for very frugal people. As an alternative to the Uzbek language, we can cite the following

proverbs: “*Bekniki – bejog’lik , boyniki – tejog’lik*”, “*Daryo-daryo qabul qil, tomchi-tomchi yubor*”.

Korean paremiology reflects ancient traditions and Korean culture. In today's Korean paremiology, the term proverb is mainly expressed by three Chinese terms – 속담, 격언 and 이언. The basis of all these terms is associated with the meanings of "word", "wisdom", "wise word".

Proverbs have long been in the spotlight as they come along with human life and experiences. That is why some Korean folk sayings have been added to the writings of ancient scholars, while others have been deliberately collected and recorded. In Korea, the term “속담” (proverb) first appeared in the second half of the seventeenth century in the remains of the books “어우야담” and “동문유행” (period of the Choson dynasty) and by the eighteenth century was widely used along with other terms [5, b.399]. However, scholars believe that in the story of the maid Ukmyon, mentioned in Chapter 5 of the “삼국유사” (1145), which records the ancient three kingdoms, the citation of the proverb “*己事之忙 , 大家之春促*” – “*내 일 바빠 한덕 방아*” (*jon kuydirmay yumush bitmas*) confirms that the articles were quoted in the written literature much earlier. The term “속담” means “속된 민족의 말” – “folk words with an inner meaning”. However, until the middle of the 15th century, when the hangeul (Korean national writing system) was created, the Korean people did not have a personal writing system, and as a result, ordinary people found it difficult to record their wise words. As a result, research on proverbs in Korea only intensified in the late twentieth century.

The history of Korean proverbs, the stages of their collection and research are as follows:

1. The first examples of proverbs in Korean written literature are found in Chapter 5 of the “삼국유사”. However, the book does not use the word “속담” in the sense of the word "wise", but “이언”.

2. Then, by the time of the Chosun Dynasty, a Chinese textbook in the book “박통사언해” quotes a proverb with the term “상언”. Only in the second half of the Choson period can we find the term “속담” in the books “어우야담” and “동문유행”.

3. The collection of proverbs dates back to the 17th century from Hong Manjong's book “순오지”. In this book, the author translates 124 popular proverbs of his time into Korean. After that, other scholars Li Deok Mu included 100 proverbs in

“청장관전사”, Jeon Yak Yong added 241 proverbs to “이담 손찬” and 422 proverbs are found in the book “동언해” whose author is unknown.

4. The first dictionary of proverbs in Korean is Choi Von Shik's book “조선이언” published in Shinmungwan in 1913, which contains more than 900 proverbs.

5. In 1922, Dongyasovon Publishing House published a collection of Kim Sanggi's “조선 속담” (Choson proverbs), which included more than 600 proverbs in addition to 900 articles in Choi Von Shik's book “조선이언”.

6. Bang Jong-hyun and Kim Sa-yeop's Dictionary of Proverbs, published in 1940, contains about 4,000 proverbs.

7. Kim Won-pyo's book of proverbs was published in 1948 and contains more than 700 proverbs.

8. Jin Seong-gi's collection of proverbs includes more than 400 articles and was published in 1959.

9. In 1962, Kyonghaksa Publishing House published a dictionary of proverbs, which contains 1256 examples of proverbs.

10. Lee Gi-mun's Dictionary of Proverbs, published in 1962, is the largest collection of Korean proverbs, with more than 7,000 proverbs.

11. The Korean Folklore Society published the book "Korean Proverbs" in 1970.

12. Son Jae-Seon's "Great Dictionary of Korean Proverbs" was published in 1980.

13. In 1993, Tongmunson Publishing House published a Dictionary of Proverbs.

14. In 1993, Chvi Chang's "Women's Proverbs" was published, and in 1995, the "Dictionary of Animal Proverbs" was published [2, p.78].

To summarize the content of the proverbs, many Korean scholars have commented as follows:

“Short words that mean lessons, experiences, joys and sorrows as an ancient folk wisdom” (*Li Hwe-sing*);

“Words that have an internal meaning that is not known when, where, or by whom they are uttered, and that have become widespread and public property as a result of a strong influence on the hearts of the people around them” (“*Great dictionary of Korean words*”);

“A concise idiomatic expression of worldly wisdom from the daily experience of ordinary people” (*Dictionary of Korean Linguistics*);

“Broadly speaking, any word that has a certain power and travels from time to time belongs to the genre of proverbs. In the narrow sense, we call proverbs words that are used to express some kind of intelligence, wisdom, imagination, vigilance, comparison, irony, or any observation experience, that is, knowledge that helps to tell the truth about human life. Therefore, proverbs are an encyclopedia of the past, a mirror of the present, a beacon of the future” (*Gang Shik-jin*) [3, p.9];

“The proverb is formed naturally in the people and reflects the wisdom, way of thinking and values of the common people's life” (*Nam Yun-shin*) [6, p.45];

“Proverbs tell us the truth of life not as a form of rebellion, but as truth. A proverb is a linguistic heritage that encompasses our historical condition” (*Jo Hin-chon*) [4, p.85];

“Proverbs are the product of universal truth and wisdom. They are not only a guide to our way of life, but also have a great persuasive and influential power, so we can say that the proverbs have an educational function that warns and awakens a person” [2, p.22].

In short, proverbs are short but powerful words that embody the culture, history, ideas, and way of life of a nation, and reflect the worldview and unique values of the people. The proverb is an eternal companion and close friend who lives and dies with the daily life of the people, making the life of the people richer, more beautiful and modern. Proverbs in Korean are one of the most complex and researched areas. When we analyze the research on proverbs in Korean folklore, we are convinced that each theory is finding its proof in science.

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